

CHANGES IN LEAF SURFACE OF COTTON VARIETIES WHICH WERE CULTIVATED THE FOLLOWING YEAR IN AREAS UNDER LEGUMES.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6623132>

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада такрорий экин Соя ва мош ўсимликлари экилган далада ўрта толали ғўза навларининг барг сатхиларини ўзгариши бўйича қимматли маълумотлар келтириб ўтилган.

Keywords: repeated plants, mung bean, soy bean, mineral fertilizers, bars, leaf level, Andijan-36, Navruz cotton variety.

Annotation: This article provides valuable information on the change in leaf levels of medium-fiber cotton varieties in the field where the second crop soybeans and mung bean are planted.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена ценная информация об изменении уровня листьев средневолокнистых сортов хлопчатника на поле, где посеяны соя второго урожая и маш.

The cotton leaf is the most important organ in the plant that exchanges gas and air. Depending on the size of the leaf blade, the type of cotton and the climatic conditions, the level ranges from 4 sq. Cm to 40 sq. Cm. At the top of the leaf blade there are 115-118 mouthparts per 1 sq. m. At the lower level, there are 245-250 pores, through which air enters the leaf, and various gases come out of these pores.

As soon as the cotton seedlings sprout to the surface, the leaf buds develop on the side of the growth point. It turns into the first leaf in 10 days, this period is 1-2 days, which can vary depending on the conditions. After 5-7 days the first petals are formed, the second petals emerge and then every 3-4 days the next leaves begin to form, the leaf formation stops during

the opening of the buds. The cotton breathes air through the leaf and evaporates the water. Instead of water evaporated through the leaves, fresh water is exchanged in turn, the water in the soil rises upwards through the roots and stems of cotton.

Carbon dioxide from the air enters it through the openings under and above the leaf blade of the cotton. Sunlight also passes through the clear thin bark of the leaf. This sunlight energy is absorbed by the chlorophyll grains in the leaf. In inorganic substances in chlorophyll granules, such as carbon dioxide and water, organic matter starch is formed under the influence of sunlight.

Carbon (carbohydrate) containing CO₂ is extracted by cotton and used to produce organic matter. In this case, the released O₂ escapes through the leaf openings. This complex process in cotton is called photosynthesis. The resulting organic matter is distributed to the elements formed by the sap, fat, protein and various other substances through the leaves.

The process of transpiration is only through the leaves, and the water in the body of the cotton is renewed 10-15 times every day, especially during the day through the leaves. This keeps the cotton body from overheating even in the hottest hot weather, and prevents the elements from spilling out of the cotton stalks.

Even in a single bush, the leaves can be different. The leaf segments are broad, narrow, medium, and large and small. If properly and timely cared for and provided with enough water and fertilizer, the cotton will grow into a "scissors" leaf, but if the cotton is not fed properly, the leaf claws will thicken and become larger, resulting in cotton buds being delayed and harvesting delayed.

Therefore, the surface of the leaf surface may change depending on the biological properties of the cotton. According to S.K.Yuldashev and M. Nazarov (1976), the leaf surface of Tashkent-1 and Tashkent-2 cotton varieties is higher than that of S-4727 and 108-F cotton varieties. In general, the acceptability of the surface area of cotton leaves is measured by the weight of the cotton crop that collected it.

Therefore, in our study, we studied the changes in the leaf surface of cotton varieties in relation to soil fertility. Depending on the amount of mineral fertilizers used in repeated crops, it was observed that the effect of the natural backgrounds formed by the decay of the root and root residues that accumulated them varied on the surface of the cotton leaf surface.

It should be noted that during the years of research, changes in the surface of the leaf surface of cotton varieties were detected during the periods of their combing, flowering and ripening.

PSUEAITI Andijan Experimental Station In the soil climate, the leaf surface area of 1 plant planted after autumn wheat (control) was 1180 cm² and 10305 m² per hectare, while during flowering and ripening these figures were 1680-14800 and 1970 cm² -16213 m², respectively. It was equal to.

It should be noted that the leaf surface area of 1 plant was determined per 1 hectare area multiplied by the actual seedling thickness data depending on the developmental stages.

The surface area of the cotton leaf surface is 1250 cm² -10412 m² in proportion to its development periods; 70-517 out of control with 1870 cm² -16325 m² and 2000 cm² -16900 m²; 190-1529 and 30 cm² -688 m² were observed to be higher. It should be noted that in cotton varieties, mineral fertilizers (even under control) were applied at the same rate (N 200, P₂O₅140, K₂O 100 kg/ha), the difference of the surface of the leaf surface from control was observed only under the influence of root and root residues left by moss (1-in the table).

Mineral fertilizers applied in the moss plant in the norms of N50, P₂O₅80, K₂O60 kg/ha in the background with a slight decrease in the surface area of cotton leaves 1250-10476 in proportion to the developmental stages; 1850-16150 and 1980 cm²-16592 m². These values are 10 cm² -379 m² higher than the control (during the ripening period), but 20 cm² -308 m² less than the background used in the beansprout N25, P₂O₅80, K₂O60 kg/ha.

The leaf surface of the cotton variety which was called Navruz is 1240-1050 cm² and 10634-10131 m² in proportion to the development periods in the background of the above 2 (options 7 and 8); 1690-1670 cm² -14500-14712 m² and 1920-10910 cm² -15452 m² -16254 m². We found that the end of the indicators (during ripening) is 20-10 cm² and 505-807 m² higher than the control, but 80-70 cm² and 148-338 m² lower than the Andijan-36 type.

Thus, the leaf surface of the Navruz cotton variety is less than that of the Andijan-36 cotton variety, but due to its biological properties, the optimal performance of this Navruz variety was observed in the background (15952 m²) applied in the norms N-25, P₂O₅-80, K₂O-60 kg / ha.

Mineral fertilizers in soybean N-60, P₂O₅90, K₂O60 kg / ha were applied during the ripening period of cotton varieties. 5-0,0 cm² and 396-152 m². It should be noted that the leaf surface of the Navruz variety differed from the control in 1 plant per 1 hectare due to the number of seedlings.

Leaf surface of cotton varieties of repeat crops effect on change (cm² / m²), according to 2011 year

1-table

№	The annual norms of mineral fertilizers				Budding	Blooming	Riping
	Types of secondary crops	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	1 ha	1 ha	1 ha
The cotton Andijan-36							
1	Control (planted)				10395	14800	16213
2	Beansprout	25	80	60	10412	16325	16900
3	Beansprout	50	80	60	10476	16150	16592
4	Soy bean	60	90	60	10150	15157	16609
5	Soy bean	90	90	60	10380	15242	16309
The cotton Navruz							
6	Control (unplanted)				9999	13950	15447
7	Beansprout	25	80	60	10639	14500	15452
8	Beansprout	50	80	60	10131	14712	16254
9	Soy bean	60	90	60	10947	14430	15599
10	Soy bean	90	90	60	15042	13876	15392

As a result of increasing mineral fertilizers in soybeans, mainly nitrogen by another 30 kg/ha, the leaf surface area of cotton varieties decreased slightly to 1965-1920 cm² and 16309-15392 m². This figure of Andijan-36 cotton variety was 96 m² per hectare higher than the control, but the leaf surface area of 1 plant of the Navruz variety was 20 cm² higher than the control. It was found that the decrease in 1 ha depends on the actual seedling thickness.

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